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ALINJA CASTLE AS AN EXAMPLE OF MEDIEVAL DEFENSIVE ARCHITECTURE OF AZERBAIJAN

Abstract

The article examines Alinja Castle as one of the important examples of medieval defensive architecture in Azerbaijan. The geographical-strategic position of the fortress, its architectural features, historical stages of development, and its role in the military defense system are investigated. At the same time, the role played by Alinja Castle in the political and military events of Azerbaijani history, especially during the medieval period, is analyzed on the basis of scientific sources. Particular attention is paid to the resistance demonstrated by the fortress during Amir Timur's campaigns to Nakhchivan, and the place of the castle in folk memory and folklore is determined. As a result of the research, it has been established that Alinja Castle was not only a military fortification but also one of the important symbols of the Azerbaijani people's history of struggle, heroism, and statehood.

Keywords: Alinja Castle, medieval architecture, defensive fortresses, Nakhchivan, Julfa district, Amir Timur, Alinja River valley, Khanagah

Introduction

Azerbaijan is one of the countries possessing ancient and rich traditions of defensive architecture. Throughout history, numerous castles, fortifications, and defensive structures were built on the territory of Azerbaijan, which was within the sphere of interest of different states. Among these architectural monuments, Alinja Castle occupies a special place. Located on the summit of the mountain bearing the same name on the right bank of the Alinja River in the territory of Julfa district of Nakhchivan, this fortress is considered one of the most magnificent examples of Azerbaijan's medieval defensive architecture due to its strategic location, architectural structure, and connection with historical events.

Alinja Castle functioned not only as a military fortification but also as one of the main centers of struggles for political power. During the Middle Ages, various states and rulers fought

seriously to possess this fortress. Sources show that the castle resisted invaders for a long time and gained fame as an unconquerable fortress, especially during Amir Timur's attacks [8, p.31].

The main purpose of the article is to determine the place of Alinja Castle in Azerbaijan's medieval defensive architecture and to investigate its architectural features and historical significance on the basis of scientific sources.

Historical-Geographical Position of Alinja Castle

Alinja Castle is located in the Julfa district of the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic, on the bank of the Alinja River, on the summit of a high and steep mountain [6, p.105]. Since the area where the fortress is located possessed natural defensive characteristics, it was considered highly favorable strategically during the Middle Ages.

Although researchers attribute the history of the fortress to the early medieval period, it is assumed that it was also used as a settlement and defense point in earlier periods [8, p.32]. In historical sources, the fortress is mentioned under various names. In some sources it appears as "Alinja," "Erinceq," "Alanciq," and "Alinjak" [6, pp.105–106].

Due to its position, Alinja Castle enabled control over the main passageways of Nakhchivan. For this reason, the fortress possessed great importance both economically and militarily-strategically. The location of the fortress on a height dominating the surrounding territories further strengthened its defensive capabilities [2, p.14].

Alinja Castle as an Example of Medieval Defensive Architecture

Among the medieval castles of Azerbaijan, Alinja Castle stands out with its magnificent defense system. The architectural structure of the fortress was closely adapted to the natural relief. The steep rocks of the mountain became the main element of defense, while artificial fortifications complemented the natural barriers [6, p.106].

The defense system of the fortress consisted of several sections. Observation points, defensive walls, narrow passages, water reservoirs, and residential buildings were located here. One of the most remarkable architectural features was the establishment of a terraced defense system. This system made it difficult for attacking forces to penetrate the fortress.

The walls of Alinja Castle were built from large stones. The thickness and height of the walls were constructed according to defensive purposes. Inside the fortress, there were special pools

[7, p.197] and storage facilities for preserving water supplies, which played an important role during long sieges.

Amir Timur's Campaigns and Alinja Castle

One of the most important events in the history of Alinja Castle, which also brought fame to the fortress, was connected with Amir Timur's campaigns to Nakhchivan. At the end of the 14th century, Amir Timur attacked Nakhchivan in order to strengthen his political authority in the region. However, Alinja Castle resisted for a long time. During this period, the Azerbaijani poet Fazlullah al-Hurufi Naimi was executed on September 2, 1394 [3].

According to historical sources, the fortress defended itself against Timur's armies for approximately fourteen years. This event is considered one of the rare examples of resistance in medieval military history [11, p.365].

One of the main reasons for the long defense of Alinja Castle was its strategic-geographical position and powerful fortification system. Although Timur's army attacked the fortress many times, the steep rocks and multi-level defense system prevented the assaults.

As a result of these events, Alinja Castle became a symbol of heroism and struggle for the Azerbaijani people. Azerbaijani scholars evaluate the defense of the fortress as an example of the people's struggle for freedom [13].

Alinja Castle in Historical Sources and Folklore

Alinja Castle occupies an important place not only in historical sources but also in Azerbaijani folklore and literature. Various legends, narratives, and information preserved in folk memory exist about the fortress. In these legends, the castle is presented as a symbol of invincibility, heroism, and freedom. These features caused it to survive in folk thought as an element of national memory.

Some researchers have noted the existence of certain references connected with Alinja Castle in the epic *The Book of Dede Korkut* [16] [9, pp.24–25].

Professor Ismayil Hajiyev, Honored Scientist of the Republic of Azerbaijan and Doctor of Historical Sciences, also notes in his studies that the Turkic-Islamic monuments of Nakhchivan are widely reflected in historical sources and states that Alinja Castle occupies a special place among these monuments [1].

The Importance of Alinja Castle in the Modern Period

During the period of independence, Alinja Castle was restored by the state and transformed into one of the important tourist routes. In 2016, extensive restoration and reconstruction works were carried out in the fortress. Today, Alinja Castle is an important historical-cultural monument attracting the attention of both local and foreign tourists. The restoration of the fortress is considered an important step in preserving Azerbaijan's historical and cultural heritage.

In the modern period, Alinja Castle functions not only as a tourist destination but also as one of the symbols of Azerbaijani statehood and national identity. Scientific events, conferences, and research conducted here create opportunities for broader study of the historical importance of the fortress.

Conclusion

As a result of the conducted research, it has been determined that Alinja Castle is one of the most important examples of medieval defensive architecture in Azerbaijan. The strategic-geographical position, architectural features, and powerful defense system of the fortress enabled it to function as an unconquerable stronghold for a long time.

Alinja Castle served not only military purposes but also played an important role in the political, cultural, and spiritual history of the Azerbaijani people. The long resistance against Amir Timur's attacks caused the fortress to become a symbol of heroism.

In the modern period, the restoration and preservation of the fortress constitute one of the important directions of Azerbaijan's historical-cultural heritage policy. Even today, Alinja Castle preserves its significance as an important symbol of the Azerbaijani people's traditions of statehood, heroic spirit, and national memory.

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